

Functional coatings of magnetic nanoparticles for Alzheimer's disease applications

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) constitutes a major challenge in the field of neurodegenerative research and requires innovative therapeutic strategies. In this study, we investigated the potential of curcumin-loaded pegylated magnetic nanoparticles as a dual-function platform for targeted therapy and imaging in AD. Curcumin, derived from the turmeric plant, has shown promise in mitigating AD pathology due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties. It inhibits amyloid-beta aggregation and reduces neuroinflammation, both critical in AD progression. Our in vitro studies showed that PMNPs significantly increase the solubility and bioavailability of curcumin, allowing for more effective cellular uptake and sustained release. The pegylation of these nanoparticles improved their biocompatibility and allows for prolonged circulation in the bloodstream, increasing their ability to reach target tissues in the brain. By using PMNPs with curcumin, we aim to create a targeted delivery system that maximizes the therapeutic effects of curcumin while minimizing potential side effects. In addition, the magnetic properties of these nanoparticles allow for non-invasive tracking and imaging using magnetic resonance techniques. This dual functionality positions PMNPs with curcumin as a promising candidate for future AD treatments, combining effective therapy with advanced diagnostic capabilities, ultimately contributing to improved patient outcomes in AD management.

4 key words:

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Pegylated magnetic nanoparticles

Iron oxide nanoparticles

Curcumin loading

Nanotechnology